

Performance of 1980 transplanted aman rice in 12 selected thana of Bangladesh

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A large-scale yield assessment study of the 1980 Bangladesh transplanted (t) aman rice crop was undertaken in 12 thana under 6 districts to determine the relative performance of new high yielding varieties (HYV), Pajam (an intermediate type between HYV and local varieties and known as Mashuri in other countries), and local varieties. A crop-cut of 5-m² area was harvested and the grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture content. A total of 453 crop-cuts were analyzed for this report. Yields of the 1980 t. aman crop were high, HYV t. aman (BR4, BR3, IR5, IR20) gave quantitatively higher yields than Pajam except in Boda thana of Dinajpur district (see figure). The performance of the local t. aman varieties was inferior to that of HYV and Pajam in all thana, except at Sherpur where the local t. aman gave a slightly higher grain yield than Pajam. On the basis of 453 sample crop-cuts, the average grain yields for HYV, Pajam, and local t. aman were 4.5, 3.9, and 3.1 t/ha. Thus, our results indicated that under current farmer management, the HYV t. aman could produce additional grain yields of 593

Yields of three groups of transplanted aman rice varieties in 12 thana of Bangladesh in 1980.

and 1,470 kg/ha in Bangladesh if grown instead of Pajam and local varieties. The study also indicated that constraints in

Khulna and Patuakhali districts limit the grain yield of t. aman rice and particularly of the modern varieties. ■

Agro-economic evaluation of farmers' direct-seeded upland rice crop at a rainfed site in Bangladesh

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Agro-economic monitoring of the farmers' rainfed aus rice crop was done

at the BRRI cropping systems research site at Alimganj, Rajshahi district, during 1980. Traditionally, farmers at this site grow local varieties of aus rice in aus rice - transplanted aman rice, aus rice - rabi (winter) crops, and aus rice - t. aman rice - rabi crops patterns. Four modern rice varieties were introduced at the site in 1980 to compare their performance with the traditional local varieties under farmers' management.

All varieties were seeded between 10 and 17 May. Seeds were broadcast for

all local and most of the modern variety fields. All farmers used fertilizers and hand weeding. Except for Purbachi, the average fertilizer rates for the modern varieties were higher (see table) than for the local varieties. Weeds were a problem in all fields and farmers hand weeded 2 to 5 times. Insecticide was used only on the modern varieties. The average field duration of local varieties ranged between 86 and 89 days; that of the modern varieties ranged from 100 to 138 days. The local varieties Hashikalmi